

Deliverable D4.1

Update of the recommendation of whole genome sequencing

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1. Executive Summary

Here we report the progress of the whole-genome sequencing (WGS) benchmark organised by CNAG, with a focus on somatic variant calling. An important goal of the project is to generate a high-confidence goldset to establish a quality baseline for the benchmark. In this deliverable we analyse how sequencing depth, library preparation, alignment settings, and pipeline-specific filters influence agreement of somatic SNV and indel calls across participating laboratories, and we summarise our findings into practical recommendations.

For goldset consolidation, the somatic variants consistently identified by all laboratories are included. For other variants, CNAG has compared all submissions to classify variants into three main categories: calls shared by all pipelines, calls shared by subsets of pipelines, and pipeline-specific singletons, focusing first on SNVs and indels. In a later phase of the project, structural variants will be validated using Nanopore sequencing so that large somatic events can also be confidently included in the goldset. Finally, for complex cases such as large indel events, possible germline leakage, overlapping and multi-base mutations, CNAG developed a variant voter tool to visually curate and validate the most challenging variants.

The construction of the goldset and initial stages of the benchmark have helped us to delineate the main lessons learned so far. Alignment and post-alignment choices (*e.g.*, local realignment as in Mutect2, trimming policies, handling of soft-clipped bases) and masking strategies (*e.g.*, Panels of Normals, ENCODE blacklist, ALT-contig use, treatment of multi-base or overlapping calls) have larger effects on callsets than modest differences in sequencing QC. Pipelines have shown consistently higher agreement for single-base SNVs than for indels, with indels exhibiting greater variability in length and breakpoint coordinates. More effort is needed for carefully comparing indels, but also multiple-base substitutions.

Updated recommendations therefore emphasise using PCR-free library preparation where possible; targeting agreed-upon coverage (80X/30X) rather than overshooting; fully documenting alignment and filtering settings; retaining or recoverably storing raw data to disentangle the impact of each choice; and clearly reporting the use of PoN, blacklists, ALT

contigs, and masking rules. Finally, although merged ultra-deep data modestly improved agreement in the calls compared to typical coverage (from 65.3% to 79.9% for substitutions and from 27.6% to 30.1% for indels), the cost–benefit ratio suggests that future somatic benchmarks could explore lower coverage for merged datasets, while concentrating effort on harmonised pipelines and transparent documentation to support reproducible and comparable somatic WGS across centres.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

Outcome 1		Contributed
Supporting the Genome EDIC WG and the 1+MG Member States on the establishment of the EDIC by carrying out the field work required to generate high quality landscape and scoping documents necessary for the compliance framework beyond the legal creation of an EDIC. These documents will drive EDIC to become operational and offer compliant access to health and genomic data, covering legal, policy, quality and security aspects of data provision.	1. A record of processing activities that captures the legitimacy of EDIC and the corresponding safeguards	No
	2. A number of documents that can be fed back to the GDI Pillar I and/or the EDIC for discussion and/or adoption to provide legal tools and policies to govern the operations for suitable and specific safeguards to ensure the protection of the rights and freedoms of the data subjects whose data are included in the EDIC for secondary use.	No
	3. A framework that can guide the implementation of national IT infrastructure to ensure the quality and the security of workflows, tools and platforms.	Yes
Outcome 2		Contributed
WP2 will analyse the EHDS Regulation and will seek close exchange with relevant projects and stakeholders to investigate the conditions for a participation in the HealthData@EU infrastructure, to give recommendations on the alignment of its policies, tools, security measures	1. An analysis of the model how the EDIC could join the EHDS, its relationship with the various stakeholders and the conditions and opportunities of such participation	No

and IT framework with the requirements of the EHDS.	2. Information on the practical consequences of the participation in the HealthData@EU infrastructure	No
	3. Engaging public health professionals, and policy makers, in the discussion of benefits and challenges of adopting genomics in healthcare systems for clinical practice and public health policies	No
	4. Documenting the implementation of genomic medicine practices in national healthcare systems	Yes
	5. Promoting the awareness, literacy level and education of citizens on genomic medicine across Europe.	No
Outcome 3		Contributed
WP3 will provide a framework of reference for genomics in healthcare that supports the decision making process, facilitating the definition of mid and long term targets and the path for genomics implementation, incorporating the feedback received from B1MG and the 1+MG experts.	1. Mapping of gaps, challenges, unmet needs and solutions from the perspective of public health and healthcare professionals, healthcare systems and national genomic healthcare implementation programmes	No
	2. Recommendations for the EDIC on the uptake and implementation of genomics for healthcare and public health	Yes
	3. A citizen's hub for dissemination of genomic medicine, promoting citizens and patients awareness, literacy and trust	No
Outcome 4		Contributed
The project will map existing studies on health economy and health technology assessments related to whole genome sequencing and other comprehensive genetic tests in healthcare. Building on the collected	1. Overview of literature and existing studies on health economy and health technology assessments related to WGS and other comprehensive genetic tests in healthcare	No

<p>best practices, and together with experts in the field, the project will develop decision trees to be tested in national settings to guide decision making related to genomics in healthcare. The long term impact of the work is the scoping of a project on economic impact of genomic medicine in healthcare to support future prioritisation in healthcare, policy makers and decisions on investment in genomic medicine.</p>	2. Decision trees tested in national settings	No
	3. Scoping of a project on economic impact of genomic medicine in healthcare	No
Outcome 5		Contributed
<p>Enhancing the 1+MG MLM for the implementation of genomics medicine in healthcare systems with updated domains and indicators, promoting its use and benchmarking by more healthcare systems. This will provide an homogeneous assessment framework that will foster the alignment of optimisation aims in healthcare systems across Europe, closing gaps, reducing asymmetries and ensuring a path towards equity of access to personalised medicine for all Europeans.</p>	1. Updated 1+MG MLM incorporating novel dimensions aligned with emerging developments in genomic medicine	No
	2. Benchmarking of the MLM by healthcare systems across Europe	No
Outcome 6		Contributed
<p>Expand the 1+MG Framework to fully define the 1+MG minimal metadata model, data standards, ontologies and quality criteria providing accessibility and maintenance, ensuring continuous alignment and support of 1+MG data use for research, innovation and policy making.</p>	1. Phenotype data model	No
	2. Genotype data model	Yes
	3. Terms of use/ELSI metadata	No
	4. Software quality indicators for components to be incorporated into the 1+MG journey.	Yes
	5. Data/metadata provenance models	No

3. Methods

3.1 Somatic Benchmark Organization

The CNAG has organized and participated in the WGS benchmark for somatic variants. In Deliverables D3.1, D3.2 and D3.3 of the B1MG we explained in more detail the design and preliminary steps of the scheme we followed. Briefly, CNAG obtained samples from the Medical University of Graz (MUG) through the EASI Genomics initiative, extracted DNA from frozen tissue and distributed the material to participant laboratories under Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs) compliant with all legal and ethical requirements. The 9 participating European centres (CGSTHLM (SciLifeLab) from Sweden, CNAG from Spain, DKFZ from Germany, DNGC and MOMA from Denmark, FIMM from Finland, Hartwig from The Netherlands, OUH from Norway, and Università di Verona from Italy), prepared libraries, sequenced samples following their own SOPs, and performed somatic variant calling using their standard pipelines. Participants then submitted their results, including SAV (Sequencing Analysis Viewer), FASTQ files and VCFs for small and large variants, to the organiser.

In a second stage, CNAG distributed the FASTQs generated in all centres to all participant laboratories, who each merged them into a single deep-coverage FASTQ and ran their pipelines on the merged data. Their resulting VCFs were returned to CNAG for building a goldset of high-confidence somatic variant calls and running the benchmark comparisons. Here we follow up on the work that has been done in the last couple years.

3.2 Test items

The benchmark is based on the analyses of the 8 Tumour/Normal pairs shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The 8 Tumour/Normal pairs used in the somatic benchmark

Sample Name Tumour	Sample Name Normal	Cancer Type
URO-002-03	URO-002-17	Clear Cell Renal Carcinoma
URO-003-01	URO-003-03	Clear Cell Renal Carcinoma
URO-004-03	URO-004-06	Clear Cell Renal Carcinoma
HNO-002-07	HNO-002-01	Head & Neck Squamous-Cell Carcinoma
THX-001-06	THX-001-02	Lung Squamous-Cell Carcinoma
THX-002-07	THX-002-01	Lung Squamous-Cell Carcinoma
HNO-004-07	HNO-004-01_02	Head & Neck Squamous-Cell Carcinoma
THX-003-09	THX-003-04	Lung Squamous-Cell Carcinoma

3.3 Quality metrics evaluation

18 Quality Metrics were measured and compared across the participating laboratories (Table 2). Following the guidelines in ISO13528:2015, the performance of each laboratory was assessed by the organiser using the z-score, where the mean of the values obtained by participants was used to set an assigned value against which each observed value obtained by the laboratories was compared. The uncertainty was estimated as the standard deviation of the observed values from the assigned value. These methods were described in detail in deliverables D3.1 and D3.2.

Table 2. Quality metrics evaluated in the somatic benchmark

QC Metric Category	QC metrics evaluated
Sequencing metrics	% bases with Q ≥ 30, % PhiX alignment, PhiX error rate, % passing filter (PF) clusters, % phasing, %prephasing
Alignment metrics	% duplicate reads, median insert size, mean coverage, evenness of coverage, % chimeras
Variant calling metrics	Ti/Tv ratio, % callability
Somatic metrics	Tumour purity, Number of somatic SNVs, Number of somatic INDELS, Number of somatic SVs, Number of somatic CNVs

3.4 Goldset generation

CNAG has currently built a goldset for sample URO-003 by integrating and curating participants' calls. We chose this sample because it has the fewest mutations and the tumour sample does not have big structural changes relative to the normal one, therefore, it could provide a good baseline to evaluate the other, more complex samples. To obtain this set of high-confidence variants, the organiser ran a series of comparisons to determine: 1) the same variants called by all the pipelines; 2) the same variants called by different subsets of pipelines; 3) the variants called by only one of the pipelines (singletons). We started working on the small variants (*i.e.*, SNVs and indels). Nanopore data will be used in a later stage to confirm the large variants only.

3.5 Benchmark variant voter

Variants consistently identified by all laboratories, despite using different calling pipelines, were included in the gold set. For other variants, CNAG established rules to determine which calls — though not shared by all methods — were still reliable enough to be included. This approach ensured that true variants detected by most methods but missed by some were recovered and retained. Finally, for complex cases such as calls with low allele frequency (AF), low allele depth (AD), or possible germline leakage, CNAG developed a variant voter tool to visually curate and validate the most challenging variants. The shiny variant voter is

accessible via secure registration and is hosted by the Deutsches Krebsforschungszentrum¹ (DKFZ) at the DENBI cloud.

3.6 Final reports

Two different reports will be generated at the end of the somatic benchmark, according to recommendations established by ISO17043:2023. One will be an individualized participant's report assessing the performance of the participant relative to other participants and the goldset, and the other will be a general report describing the overall benchmark design, development, results and overall conclusions. In the reports, CNAG will estimate the F1, Precision and Recall metrics for all laboratories with respect to the goldset. To do so, CNAG has generated a nextflow pipeline for the benchmark that uses standard performance tools: hap.py, prep.py, and rep.py², for the small variants (SNVs and indels), and truvari for the large variants (structural and copy number variants).

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 1+MG WG4 Somatic Benchmark

4.1.1 QC metrics

In the first steps of the somatic benchmark, we assessed the performance of the participating laboratories by using 18 quality metrics that were divided into 4 main categories: 1) sequencing metrics, 2) alignment metrics, 3) variant calling metrics, and 4) somatic metrics (Table 2). The full detail of how these metrics were evaluated was presented in deliverables D3.1, D3.2 and D3.3.

4.1.2 Participant Laboratory Performance Evaluation

4.1.2.1 Performance evaluation using z- scores

Following the recommendations of the 1993 Harmonized Protocol of the IUPAC (Thomson and Wood 1993), and given their wide applicability and acceptance, we used z-scores to compare the observations of the ILC participants. Z-scores are defined as: $z = (x - x_a)/r_p$, where x is the value observed by the participant, x_a is the mean of the observations of the participants that operate at a higher metrological level, such as those who are ISO 15189 or/and ISO/ICE 17025 accredited, and r_p is the standard deviation of the observations from the mean.

¹ <https://www.dkfz.de/>

² <https://github.com/Illumina/hap.py>

If applicable, a threshold was assigned to each metric, which was either upper, lower, or both. The thresholds were set for each metric based on the Z-score calculation. As explained, the Z-score indicates how much the measurement of each metric deviates from the group. The outcome of the test was considered “Acceptable” if the absolute value of the Z-score was lower than 2 standard deviation units. If the absolute value of Z-score was higher than 3 standard deviation units, the test result was considered “Unacceptable”. An absolute Z-score in the range between 2 and 3 standard deviation units was deemed as “Questionable”.

4.1.3 Sequencing and bioinformatics pipelines

4.1.3.1 Sequence Analysis Viewer (SAV) and FASTQ data analysis

SAV files were used to extract the sequencing metrics using INTEROP V1.1.23 and FASTQC/0.11.9-JAVA-11 was used to obtain the corresponding sequencing quality metrics.

4.1.3.2 Alignment and downsampling

Sequencing data received from the participants was pre-processed following the Broad Institute’s best practices for variant calling (DePristo 2011). Briefly, sequencing FASTQ files were aligned to the human reference genome version GRCh38³ with BWA (Li 2013), duplicated reads were marked with Picard Tools⁴ and base qualities were recalibrated with GATK (DePristo 2011).

The data of each participant was downsampled to 100 gigabases with Picard’s DownsampleSam, duplicated reads were marked and quality control was assessed as before. It is worth to remark that the downsampling was conducted under the assumption that all reads had a length of 150 nucleotides and, thus, data from participants that had deviated from the sequencing specifications/indications, e.g. by applying adaptors trimming, produced fewer aligned bases.

4.1.3.2 Quality Control

At this stage, exhaustive quality control of the received data was performed using the standard programs from the Picard bundle. Additionally, Alfred (Rausch 2019) and goleft indexcov (Pedersen 2017) were also employed. Coverage metrics and identification of callable regions were done with Mosdepth (Pedersen 2018) and MultiQC (Ewels 2016) was used to gather all the metrics in a single report per sample and participant.

³ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genomes/all/GCA/000/001/405/GCA_000001405.15_GRCh38/seqs_for_alignment_pipelines.ucsc_ids/GCA_000001405.15_GRCh38_no_alt_analysis_set.fna.gz

⁴ <http://broadinstitute.github.io/picard>

4.1.4 Bioinformatic Goldset construction for SNVs and Indels

4.1.4.1 From merged FASTQ to multiple VCF comparisons

Based on the results of the quality metrics assessed in 3.3 Quality metrics evaluation, we selected the callsets of 5 Participating laboratories (CNAG, DNGC, DKFZ, Hartwig, OUH) who sequenced 8 T/N pairs, and of 1 participant (Verona), who sequenced only 4 T/N pairs. These participants were asked to merge the FASTQs produced by all the laboratories, run their different variant calling pipelines and return to CNAG their resulting VCFs for small variants and TSV files for large variants. The expected coverage of the merged FASTQ files was ~600X.

5 variant callers frequently cited in the literature were used by the different participating laboratories to identify somatic single nucleotide variants and short insertions and deletions: Strelka2 (Kim 2018), Mutect2 (Benjamin et al. 2019 Dragen), Illumina Dragen software v4.2⁵ and three proprietary pipelines, WiGiTS⁶ developed by Hartwig Medical Foundation (HMF), the SNVs⁷ and indel⁸ pipelines developed by the Deutsches Krebsforschungszentrum (DKFZ).

4.1.5 Manually curated somatic variants for Goldset construction

4.1.5.1 Somatic mutation base and read sample statistics (from merged VCFs)

The merged 8 T/N pairs were analysed to get overall per sample estimates: total number of reads, total number of bases, % bases mapped, error rate %, read length.

4.1.5.2 Per sample mutation statistics

For each of the 8 T/N pairs, and each of the pipelines used in the somatic benchmark, we estimated the number of somatic single-base mutations (SNVs) and somatic insertion/deletion mutations (indels).

4.1.5.3 Analysis of the overlap of pipeline calls

Having obtained the statistics for the number and type of mutations, we estimated how many mutations were called the same by 1) all pipelines, 2) different subsets of pipelines, and 3) by only one of the pipelines (singletons). This overlap analysis allowed us to establish how many consensus, majority, doubleton and singleton mutations there are. Consensus calls are the easiest to identify by any variant caller software and typically have a high likelihood to be called with high confidence. Consensus calls are the backbone of the

⁵ <https://help.dragen.illumina.com/reference/citing-dragen>

⁶ <https://github.com/hartwigmedical/hmftools>

⁷ <https://github.com/DKFZ-ODCF/SNVCallingWorkflow>

⁸ <https://github.com/DKFZ-ODCF/IndelCallingWorkflow>

goldset. Calls that are not identified by all callers could have been missed by one or a few programs depending on the specific search algorithms and thresholds implemented by the different software packages. These calls can be verified and retained to be part of the goldset. Finally, doubletons and singletons, those mutations called by only one or two callers, need a more careful inspection to be validated. The expectation is that the high coverage obtained with the merged data (~600X) will allow the detection of true mutations, even those present at very low frequencies.

4.1.5.4 Development of an online tool for the manual curation of variants

A secure online shiny API was created for the manual curation of the mutations that were ambiguously called by the variant callers used, including non-consensus mutations. Excluded from this curation process were calls discarded due to either being caused by germline leakage, being sequencing or calling artefacts, being present at extremely low allele frequencies, among other causes.

4.1.5.5 Votes on URO-003

Of the 8 T/N pair samples, two (NHO-002 and URO-002) were set aside from the manual curation because they showed signs of MSI and large translocation events, respectively, that would make it very hard to analyse with the current tools. To begin with the curation process and as a first test case, we chose the sample URO-003, one of the samples with fewest mutations, to use with the shiny mutation voting tool. Experts are shown IGV-like screenshots of the URO-003 mutations, in both the normal and the tumour samples simultaneously, for the same position. The experts need to answer the question “Is this a somatic mutation (e.g., A -> G)?” and they can choose between the following options for assessing the event: 1) Yes, it is the somatic mutation shown above, 2) No, it is a different somatic mutation + comment field, 3) No, it is germline leakage, 4) None of the above + sub options a) Issues with coverage, b) Alignment issues, c) Complex events, d) Screenshot is inconclusive. Once the experts finish voting, CNAG will analyse the agreement among the votes, and a decision will be made whether to include the mutation in the goldset and consider it validated.

5. Results

Here we cover the work that has been done for the construction of the goldsets.

5.1 Bioinformatics Goldset construction for somatic SNVs and Indels

5.1.1 From merged FASTQ to multiple VCF comparisons

The individual FASTQs produced by the participants differed widely in terms of coverage for both the tumour and normal samples. The expected coverage for the tumour samples was

80X and 30X for the normal, which would result in a tumour/normal ratio of ~2.6. Figure 1 shows the variability of the tumour/normal ratio in the 8 T/N pairs across the 6 laboratories that participated in the construction of the goldset (*i.e.*, CNAG, DKFZ, DNGC, Hartwig, OUH and Verona). The variability in coverage at the individual FASTQ files had an impact in the merged FASTQ files, such that the laboratories that sequenced more in their individual FASTQs contributed more data to the merged FASTQ files. This has the potential to bias somewhat the data used to run the different sequencing protocols by the participating laboratories. The sequencing done in all centres was uniformly of high quality.

Figure 1. Variability in the coverage of the individual FASTQ files per sample and participating laboratory. Colour coded bars: **CNAG (red)**, **DKFZ (orange)**, **DNGC (pink)**, **Hartwig (purple)**, **OUH (blue)**, **Verona (dark green)**.

5.1.2 Somatic mutation base and reads statistics

For each of the 8 T/N pairs, Tables 3 – 10 contain the sample statistics at the base and read level submitted by the participating laboratories, where available. NA stands for the data not submitted by the participating centre to the organizer.

Table 3: Sample HNO-002 sequencing and alignment summary statistics

NORMAL	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH	Verona
Total reads	5464857300	NA	9070432398	NA	9117789359	9117789359
Non primary	29297653	NA	42163662	NA	48952744	48952744
Duplicated %	7.3	NA	10.62	NA	10.65	10.7
Mapped %	99.6	NA	99.49	NA	99.5	99.5
zeroMQ %	4.9	NA	4.75	NA	4.89	4.9
Read Length	151	NA	151	NA	151	151
Total Bases	8.28E+11	NA	1.38E+12	NA	1.38E+12	1.38099E+12
Bases mapped %	97.7	NA	98.16	NA	97.63	97.6
Error rate %	0.68	NA	0.708	NA	0.694	0.69
TUMOR	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH_merge	Verona
Total reads	14509206327	NA	23073505420	NA	21680347668	21680347668
Non primary	72859885	NA	100072494	NA	109157053	109157053
Duplicated %	8.9	NA	11.98	NA	12.17	12.2
Mapped %	99.6	NA	99.46	NA	99.55	99.6
zeroMQ %	4.5	NA	4.37	NA	4.47	2.5
Read Length	151	NA	151	NA	151	151
Total Bases	2.20E+11	NA	3.51E+12	NA	3.28E+12	3.28164E+12
Bases mapped %	97.8	NA	98.20	NA	97.81	97.8
Error rate %	0.66	NA	0.713	NA	0.668	0.67

Table 4: Sample HNO-004 sequencing and alignment summary statistics

NORMAL	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH	Verona
Total reads	4884055480	7550621518	9105048704	NA	8699911310	8699911310
Non primary	26354009	0	42586351	NA	47207632	47207632
Duplicated %	6.5	9.9	9.54	NA	9.62	9.6
Mapped %	99.6	99.9	99.52	NA	99.58	99.6
zeroMQ %	4.6	5.7	4.45	NA	4.57	4.6
Read Length	151	151	151	NA	151	151
Total Bases	7.40E+11	1.14E+12	1.38E+12	NA	1.32E+12	1.31819E+12
Bases mapped %	97.8	103.3	98.21	NA	97.76	97.8
Error rate %	0.63	0.68	0.684	NA	0.649	0.65
TUMOR	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH_merge	Verona
Total reads	12895515420	15610027414	NA	NA	17337199459	17337199459
Non primary	69371674	0	NA	NA	92533685	92533685
Duplicated %	8.2	10.5	NA	NA	10.29	10.3
Mapped %	99.2	99.9	NA	NA	99.16	99.2
zeroMQ %	4.5	5.8	NA	NA	4.46	4.5
Read Length	151	151	NA	NA	151	151
Total Bases	1.95E+12	2.37E+12	NA	NA	2.63E+12	2.62731E+12
Bases mapped %	97.3	102.9	NA	NA	97.37	97.4
Error rate %	0.64	0.68	NA	NA	0.644	0.64

Table 5: Sample THX-001 sequencing and alignment summary statistics

NORMAL	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH	Verona
Total reads	5512754719	9121868808	10293413202	NA	9891513818	9891513818
Non primary	29164093	0	47169191	NA	52324252	52324252
Duplicated %	6.9	11.2	10.72	NA	11.05	11
Mapped %	99.6	99.9	99.49	NA	99.55	99.6
zeroMQ %	4.7	5.9	4.56	NA	4.72	4.7
Read Length	151	151	151	NA	151	151
Total Bases	8.35E+11	1.38083E+12	1.56E+12	NA	1.50E+12	1.49705E+12
Bases mapped %	97.9	103	98.23	NA	97.78	97.8
Error rate %	0.66	0.7	0.706	NA	0.67	0.67
TUMOR	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH_merge	Verona
Total reads	14757947176	19340761722	21964522406	NA	21136067714	21136067714
Non primary	77504673	0	95055298	NA	110719534	110719534
Duplicated %	8.8	11.8	11.52	NA	11.71	11.7
Mapped %	99.5	99.9	99.43	NA	99.48	99.5
zeroMQ %	4.7	5.9	4.54	NA	4.69	4.7
Read Length	151	151	151	NA	151	151
Total Bases	2.23E+12	2.92732E+12	3.33E+12	NA	3.20E+12	3.19841E+12
Bases mapped %	97.6	102.9	98.21	NA	97.58	97.6
Error rate %	0.68	0.7	0.709	NA	0.677	0.68

Table 6: Sample THX-002 sequencing and alignment summary statistics

NORMAL	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH	Verona
Total reads	5496039331	8808806696	10221683488	NA	9870373103	8877290837
Non primary	30268804	0	49479618	NA	54407769	49226499
Duplicated %	6.8	10.7	10.24	NA	10.39	10.2
Mapped %	99.6	99.9	99.48	NA	99.52	99.5
zeroMQ %	4.5	5.6	4.38	NA	4.52	4.5
Read Length	151	151	151	NA	151	151
Total Bases	8.32E+11	1.33514E+12	1.55E+12	NA	1.50E+12	1.34548E+12
Bases mapped %	97.8	102.9	98.20	NA	97.72	97.7
Error rate %	0.65	0.69	0.701	NA	0.668	0.66
TUMOR	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH_merge	Verona
Total reads	14622478294	18734101810	21137070766	NA	20494362714	18203244766
Non primary	76314431	0	93719220	NA	106955969	95126581
Duplicated %	8.2	11.1	10.85	NA	10.92	10.7
Mapped %	99.5	99.9	99.52	NA	99.54	99.5
zeroMQ %	4.3	5.4	4.17	NA	4.32	4.3
Read Length	151	151	151	NA	151	151
Total Bases	2.21E+12	2.83723E+12	3.21E+12	NA	3.10E+12	2.75707E+12
Bases mapped %	97.8	103.1	98.34	NA	97.81	97.8
Error rate %	0.65	0.68	0.672	NA	0.647	0.64

Table 7: Sample THX-003 sequencing and alignment summary statistics

NORMAL	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH	Verona
Total reads	4889977055	7988068736	8472757276	NA	8807973112	8807973112
Non primary	26816959	0	39701025	NA	48042757	48042757
Duplicated %	6.7	11	10.33	NA	10.6	10.6
Mapped %	99.5	99.9	99.52	NA	99.5	99.5
zeroMQ %	4.6	5.7	4.45	NA	4.61	4.6
Read Length	151	151	151	NA	151	151
Total Bases	7.41E+11	1.20987E+12	1.28E+12	NA	1.33E+12	1.33368E+12
Bases mapped %	97.8	103	98.40	NA	97.81	97.8
Error rate %	0.63	0.68	0.655	NA	0.649	0.65
TUMOR	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH_merge	Verona
Total reads	12759154285	15264188868	19026556438	NA	16923308543	16923308543
Non primary	74313157	0	89867944	NA	96359534	96359534
Duplicated %	8.5	11.1	10.72	NA	10.75	10.7
Mapped %	99.5	100	99.48	NA	99.54	99.5
zeroMQ %	4.6	5.6	4.38	NA	4.52	4.5
Read Length	151	151	152	NA	151	151
Total Bases	1.94E+12	2.3178E+12	2.90E+12	NA	2.57E+12	2.56833E+12
Bases mapped %	97.5	102.8	98.30	NA	97.63	97.6
Error rate %	0.65	0.67	0.677	NA	0.642	0.64

Table 8: Sample URO-002 sequencing and alignment summary statistics

NORMAL	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH	Verona
Total reads	5509663990	9268180040	12359354084	NA	10469318220	9355716094
Non primary	31766132	0	63191968	NA	60800624	54629457
Duplicated %	6.8	11.2	12.35	NA	11.05	10.9
Mapped %	99.5	99.9	99.48	NA	99.45	99.4
zeroMQ %	4.7	6	4.51	NA	4.66	4.7
Read Length	151	151	151	NA	151	151
Total Bases	8.34E+11	1.40322E+12	1.87E+12	NA	1.58E+12	1.41644E+12
Bases mapped %	97.7	103.3	98.22	NA	97.55	97.6
Error rate %	0.67	0.74	0.707	NA	0.699	0.7
TUMOR	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH_merge	Verona
Total reads	14722477657	18348023080	20674952102	NA	20488320365	17762701211
Non primary	83710519	0	105113774	NA	116827873	100704911
Duplicated %	9.1	11.9	10.74	NA	11.83	11.6
Mapped %	99.5	99.9	99.44	NA	99.48	99.5
zeroMQ %	4.7	6	4.55	NA	4.68	4.7
Read Length	151	151	152	NA	151	151
Total Bases	2.23E+12	2.7764E+12	3.14E+12	NA	3.10E+12	2.68802E+12
Bases mapped %	97.6	103.2	98.13	NA	97.56	97.6
Error rate %	0.68	0.73	0.721	NA	0.683	0.68

Table 9: Sample URO-003 sequencing and alignment summary statistics

NORMAL	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH_merge	Verona
Total reads	4927049924	7946821868	9475389742	NA	8906101235	8906101235
Non primary	27971898	0	47761327	NA	50800955	50800955
Duplicated %	7.3	11.8	11.01	NA	11.31	11.3
Mapped %	99.5	99.9	99.33	NA	99.36	99.4
zeroMQ %	4.9	6.2	4.75	NA	4.91	4.9
Read Length	151	151	152	NA	151	151
Total Bases	7.46E+11	1.20447E+12	1.44E+12	NA	1.35E+12	1.34932E+12
Bases mapped %	97.7	103.3	98.00	NA	97.57	97.6
Error rate %	0.65	0.71	0.705	NA	0.666	0.67
TUMOR	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH_merge	Verona
Total reads	13106686131	17569237544	21284321398	NA	19935659357	19935659357
Non primary	74799552	0	108902147	NA	114243212	114243212
Duplicated %	8.8	12.5	12.01	NA	12.24	12.2
Mapped %	99.6	99.9	99.55	NA	99.57	99.6
zeroMQ %	4.9	6.3	4.79	NA	4.9	4.9
Read Length	151	151	152	NA	151	151
Total Bases	1.99E+12	2.66077E+12	3.24E+12	NA	3.02E+12	3.0181E+12
Bases mapped %	97.8	103.3	98.25	NA	97.78	97.8
Error rate %	0.68	0.74	0.711	NA	0.681	0.68

Table 10: Sample URO-004 sequencing and alignment summary statistics

NORMAL	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH	Verona
Total reads	4884015291	7429254056	8204481848	NA	8482300710	8482300710
Non primary	26951644	0	39473549	NA	47031738	47031738
Duplicated %	6.7	10.5	9.80	NA	10.06	10.1
Mapped %	99.5	99.9	99.47	NA	99.45	99.5
zeroMQ %	4.5	5.6	4.35	NA	4.49	4.5
Read Length	151	151	151	NA	151	151
Total Bases	7.40E+11	1.1257E+12	1.24E+12	NA	1.28E+12	1.28471E+12
Bases mapped %	97.9	103.1	98.36	NA	97.79	97.8
Error rate %	0.62	0.67	0.647	NA	0.641	0.64
TUMOR	CNAG	DKFZ	DNGC	Hartwig	OUH_merge	Verona
Total reads	12832010383	15249533564	18362747246	NA	17249539405	17249539405
Non primary	73612033	0	92466687	NA	98792737	98792737
Duplicated %	9	11.9	11.27	NA	11.5	11.5
Mapped %	99.4	99.9	99.47	NA	99.45	99.4
zeroMQ %	4.6	5.8	4.48	NA	4.62	4.6
Read Length	151	151	152	NA	151	151
Total Bases	1.94E+12	2.30998E+12	2.79E+12	NA	2.61E+12	2.61198E+12
Bases mapped %	97.7	102.9	98.27	NA	97.73	97.7
Error rate %	0.66	0.71	0.694	NA	0.669	0.67

5.1.3 Per sample mutation statistics

The mutation calls produced by 6 participant laboratories (*i.e.*, CNAG, DKFZ, DNGC, Hartwig, OUH and Verona) with their own individually called data and running their own SOP pipelines, resulted in very different estimates of substitutions and indels.

Adding up the calls obtained individually by all centres, we observed that the highest number of mutations was found for sample HNO-002 with 103,995 substitutions and 700,250 indels (Table 11). On the other hand, the lowest number of substitutions was obtained for URO-003 (13,791), and the lowest number of indels for URO-002 (2,620). It is noteworthy that even if HNO-002 shows by far the highest number of mutations, a large fraction of those are called by individual pipelines (*i.e.*, singleton calls). CNAG alone contributed 145,366 indels out of the 700 thousand total indels. When we asked which proportion of mutations were called in common among the participant laboratories, we saw that the highest percentage of shared substitutions (65.3%) and indels (27.6%) was obtained for the sample THX-003 (Table 11). On the other hand, sample URO-002 had the fewest shared mutations among all centres, with 83.4% private substitutions and 92.1% private indels.

Table 11. Number and percentage of the estimated substitutions and indels obtained from the calling on individual FASTQs

Sample	Combined Total		% All agree on*		% of private calls	
	substitutions	indels	substitutions	indels	substitutions	indels
HNO-002	103,995	700,250	40.5%	4.3%	22.3%	31.2%
HNO-004 *	20,886	6,516	52.3%	6.6%	33.4%	60.5%
THX-001	38,645	11,410	47.2%	8.5%	38.6%	35.0%
THX-002	79,280	6,222	68.7%	24.0%	11.8%	40.9%
THX-003 *	94,251	7,737	65.3%	27.6%	10.0%	42.2%
URO-002	14,594	2,620	4.0%	1.3%	83.4%	92.1%
URO-003 *	13,791	3,007	37.8%	19.6%	50.8%	63.0%
URO-004 *	14,793	3,188	23.3%	19.7%	58.4%	64.4%

*Indicate the samples that Verona did not sequence, so there is one fewer pipeline assessed

A similar pattern was observed when we analysed the calls obtained from the merged data called by all centres (Table 12). HNO-002 had again the highest number of mutations obtained using the merged data, with 108,306 substitutions and 981,315 indels. At the other end, the lowest number of mutations was again URO-002, with 7,520 substitutions and 1,179 indels. Looking at the agreement among participating laboratories, the highest percentage of shared calls was again observed in sample THX-003, with 79.9% shared substitutions and 30.1% shared indels. Inversely, sample URO-002 had again the highest percentage of privately called mutations, with 53.6% private substitutions and 77.2% private indels.

Table 12. Number and percentage of the estimated substitutions and indels obtained from the calling on merged FASTQs

Sample	Combined Total		% All agree on		% of private calls	
	substitutions	indels	substitutions	indels	substitutions	indels
HNO-002	108,306	981,315	41.7%	3.4%	24.5%	50.4%
HNO-004	18,153	6,614	67.2%	7.8%	20.3%	65.5%
THX-001	35,040	13,584	50.0%	6.8%	24.2%	61.7%
THX-002	81,125	6,207	76.1%	26.0%	7.7%	45.3%
THX-003	94,118	7,550	79.9%	30.1%	5.1%	39.4%
URO-002 *	7,520	1,179	2.1%	0.3%	53.6%	77.2%
URO-003	10,924	2,746	52.9%	20.8%	33.7%	56.4%
URO-004	11,782	2,667	45.2%	24.3%	31.6%	49.3%

*Indicates the sample that Hartwig did not sequence, so there is one fewer pipeline assessed

We expected to observe more calls and with higher support in using the merged data than with calls from individually called data, given the substantial increase in coverage (*e.g.*, for tumour samples, from ~80X to ~600X). This was indeed the case for substitutions in half of the samples (HNO-002, URO-002, URO-003 and URO-004), and in only 3 of the samples for indels (HNO-002, HNO-004 and THX-003). However, in both the individual and merged calls we saw a high number of private calls (Table 11 and Table 12). Consequently, we saw a low number of shared calls among the participant laboratories. Moreover, when we looked at both the individual and merged calls combined (Table 13), we only found an increase in

substitution calls supported by all the 16 pipelines compared in sample THX-002 (60.2%). Noticeably, when we looked at the combined calls from 16 pipelines, 8 ran on individual and 8 on merged data, the sample URO-002 did not have a single call supported by all pipelines, neither substitutions, nor indels. Instead, we observed 78.2% and 89.4% of private calls for substitutions and indels respectively.

Table 13. Number and percentage of the estimated substitutions and indels obtained from the combined calling on individual and merged FASTQs

Sample	Combined Total		% All agree on		% of private calls	
	substitutions	indels	substitutions	indels	substitutions	indels
HNO-002	129,163	1,078,460	29.8%	2.1%	26.3%	34.3%
HNO-004*	24,794	9,995	43.3%	3.9%	39.8%	62.2%
THX-001	48,127	18,231	32.4%	4.3%	41.7%	51.3%
THX-002	88,773	8,902	60.2%	15.2%	14.8%	51.7%
THX-003*	101,604	10,217	59.6%	17.9%	11.3%	47.9%
URO-002**	18,859	3,570	0%	0%	78.2%	89.4%
URO-003*	17,702	4,568	28.9%	11.2%	56.7%	69.2%
URO-004*	19,538	4,638	17.4%	12.2%	57.2%	68.3%

*Indicate the samples that Verona did not sequence, so there is one fewer pipeline assessed

** Indicates the sample that Hartwig did not sequence, so there is one fewer pipeline assessed

From the results above, two important decisions were made. First, we investigated more thoroughly the mutations found in samples HNO-002 and URO-002, as they had the highest number of private calls and because they had either too many (HNO-002) or too few mutations (URO-002) relative to samples of the same tumour type and compared across samples. When we further characterized these two samples, we detected signals of MSI in HNO-002 and complex events involving large rearrangements and possible translocations between chromosomes 1 and 3 in URO-002. As the main goal of this project is to obtain a set of high confidence calls, we decided to continue our analysis of the 6 remaining samples and leave aside HNO-002 and URO-002 to be done later, as these two samples will require a more thorough examination and a lot more work. Second, given that most of the private

calls on merged data came from the calls done by CNAG and DNGC, we decided to exclude those calls from the analysis. By removing them, the proportion of calls shared by the remaining pipelines (DKFZ, Hartwig, OUH, Verona) increased, for example, in the case of THX-003, to 82.6% shared substitutions and 42.8% indels, and the private calls decreased to 7.5% and 32.4% in substitutions and indels respectively (Table 14).

Table 14. Number and percentage of the estimated substitutions and indels obtained from the merged FASTQs called by DKFZ, Hartwig, OUH and Verona

Sample	Combined Total		% all agree on		% of private calls	
	substitutions	indels	substitutions	indels	substitutions	indels
HNO-002	84,108	450,296	58.1%	8.6%	25.8%	61.6%
HNO-004	16,828	2,971	72.9%	17.7%	18.3%	54.0%
THX-001	30,238	6,159	68.3%	17.8%	19.7%	51.5%
THX-002	78,757	4,128	79.0%	39.7%	10.9%	38.4%
THX-003	91,957	5,344	82.6%	42.8%	7.5%	32.4%
URO-002 *	5,298	626	41.6%	8.1%	44.4%	82.3%
URO-003	9,710	1,759	60.2%	32.6%	31.2%	50.0%
URO-004	10,581	1,976	52.8%	33.0%	32.1%	46.3%

*Indicates the sample that Hartwig did not sequence, so there is one fewer pipeline assessed

5.1.4 Analysis of the overlap of pipeline calls

With the merged data called by DKFZ, Hartwig, OUH, and Verona, we investigated how many mutations were called in agreement by 1) all 4 pipelines, 2) different subsets of those pipelines, and 3) by only one of the pipelines (*i.e.*, singletons).

Due to limited space, here we present only the results obtained for sample URO-003. Figure 3 shows the upset plot of the substitutions called on the merged data. In golden colour, we see the bar corresponding to the substitutions called by all 4 pipelines. Those 5,844 substitutions can therefore be retained as good candidates for the goldset. The next category comprises the 418 substitutions that were called by 3 out of 4 pipelines (*i.e.*, silver-coloured bars) and have a good potential to be part of the goldset after validation. The bronze-coloured bars correspond to the 418 substitutions called by 2 of the 4 pipelines and need further examination to be included in the goldset. Finally, the red bars are the

singleton substitutions called by only 1 of the pipelines and need to be carefully examined by human experts before validation.

Figure 3. Overlap of substitutions called on merged data for sample URO-003 by DKFZ, Hartwig, OUH and Verona

Figure 4 presents the overlap analysis of the indels called by DKFZ, Hartwig, OUH, and Verona from merged data. The golden bar represents the 573 indels called by all 4 pipelines, the silver bars to the 170 indels called by 3 out of 4 pipelines, the bronze bars to the 136 indels called by 2 out of 4 pipelines and the red bars are the 880 indels that are called by only one pipeline. Before keeping any calls in the goldset, all variants called are being inspected by human experts.

Figure 4. Overlap of indels called on merged data for sample URO-003 by DKFZ, Hartwig, OUH and Verona

5.2 Manual curation of goldset somatic variants for SNVs and Indels

5.2.1 Development of an online tool for the manual curation of variants

To obtain a set of variants called with the highest confidence, we invited human experts to validate the mutations called by the pipelines of all participating laboratories. Genomic screenshots of variants were curated by human experts, who were able to cast a vote validating or rejecting the call (Figure 5). At present, experts are voting on the variants of sample URO-003. Once we analyse and compare the results, we will be able to decide on the set of variants at the highest confidence and we will be able to learn which are the somatic variant callers, and which are the settings that produce the most reliable and robust calls. For the moment we have a preliminary assessment of the most important variables that

produced the variants called by all the pipelines, and by a majority of votes that validate the calls.

Figure 5. Example of a variant voter screenshot with the options to vote

6. Discussion

6.1 Preliminary guidelines for the construction of a goldset of somatic SNVs and Indels

First take-home message: differences in sequencing QC metrics do not appear to affect the quality of the somatic variant calling, as all participating laboratories achieved acceptable results, and their measured z-scores do not significantly deviate from the mean and indicative values. From the periodic Inter Laboratory Comparison that is run by CNAG in parallel to this somatic benchmark, we have a few recommendations regarding sequencing and library preparation to ensure sufficient quality. The most important is to use a PCR-free protocol because many PCR cycles can introduce errors in the calls. Also, insert-size should be more than the sum of the paired reads, we recommend following the suggested median insert size.

Second: the choice of alignment settings does have an impact in the somatic variant calling. The main difference among the pipelines run by the participants is between those that perform local realignment, as Mutect2 does, and those that do not realign. Local realignment affects indels more than they do single-base substitutions, as they can shift

positions with respect to non-realigned sites. Trimming is another choice that can result in differences in the calls. For building the goldsets, we asked participants to submit raw data, but some SOPs include trimming or handling adaptors differently (*e.g.*, Dragen), which can introduce differences. It is argued that most callers can post-process trimming, but we observed a few mismatches possibly due to it. Finally, soft clipping can further introduce artefactual differences in the called variants. As far as we know, there is no standard or recommended way to handle the soft-clipped bases.

Third: we asked participant laboratories to sequence at 30X for normal samples and at 80X for tumour ones. However, a couple of laboratories sequenced ~ 3 times higher depth than the expected, and 1 lab sequenced at a depth below what was required. This resulted in very different contributions to the data being used to merge the FASTQs and build the goldset (Figure 1). As a result, some pipelines may weigh more heavily in the calls being evaluated, and others may be underrepresented.

Fourth: another decision affecting somatic variant calling is the choice of masking or filtering according to the priorities of SOPs. The use of a Panel of Normals (PoN) significantly affects the variants that are called, as pre-selected sites are not called, based on prior knowledge of which sites are germline variants. Other forms of SOP-specific masking include the use of standardized filters such as the ENCODE blacklist that filters out known regions in the human genome that contain anomalous, un-structured, high signal/read counts in WGS experiments. Also, the use of ALT contigs can vary between callers, which may result in different variants being called. Finally, calling multiple-base and overlapping mutations is handled very differently in each SOP pipeline, with some choosing not to call them at all or making arbitrary decisions about how to call them.

7. Conclusions & Impact

7.1 Update of the recommendations of WGS for somatic variant calling

One of the first conclusions of the somatic benchmark is that differences in library preparation and sequencing do not impact the somatic variant calling significantly, as all participant laboratories achieved high quality level with their SOPs. The only parameter that has some effect is the choice of PCR-free protocols, that are recommended over running PCR cycles. Alignment settings affect the somatic calls in diverse ways and with variable impacts. The bioinformatics pipelines of participants do vary significantly in terms of alignment parameters and it would be hard to establish an overall recommendation, as different pipelines are designed with different objectives. Nevertheless, one recommendation is to keep track of all choices of alignment and post-alignment to be able

to evaluate the impact of each setting separately. To this end, keeping the raw data for reference, or using settings that allow to recover the original alignment after local realignment are a good recommendation. For coverage, the guideline is to aim for a fair comparison among participants by achieving the expected coverage and not incurring in unnecessary costs. Finally, be aware that any pipeline-specific choices should be well documented to account for the use of PoN, ALT contigs, blacklists or any pre-filtering or masking settings, as they all have an impact in the final somatic variants called.

7.2 Preliminary conclusions of the goldset construction of somatic variants

A clear conclusion is that all the bioinformatics pipelines compared are much better at calling SNVs than indels, as the latter show more variability at calling the event's length and exact coordinates. Single-base substitutions are the low hanging fruit for all the evaluated callers, however, multiple- or overlapping substitutions pose a greater challenge and different callers appear to make pipeline-specific decisions for handling either case.

We expected to gain confidence in the calls obtained using the merged datasets (~600X coverage), but the increase in the number of shared calls and the decrease in the number of private calls was only modest, relative to the individual somatic variant calling (~80X coverage). Comparing the variants called by all the participants' pipelines, calls obtained with the merged data resulted in 79.9% shared substitutions and 30.1% shared indels, compared to the 65.3% and 27.6% shared substitutions and indels, respectively, obtained from individual calls. Perhaps in future somatic benchmarks, shallower coverage in merged FASTQs (< ~600X) can be assessed to achieve the best compromise of sensitivity/cost.

We hope that the current work will serve the community as a ground-truth reference for benchmarking current and future pipelines, providing evidence for more harmonised minimum requirements for coverage, QC, and transparent documentation across Europe.

Ideally, it can also serve as practical guidance on cost-effective design of similar efforts by helping with the identification of systematic weaknesses (particularly in indel calling and complex events) that need extra caution and thereby raise the standard for whole-genome somatic variant calling and analysis.

8. Next steps

We will finish the manual curation of mutations in the remaining 7 T/N pair samples and build a goldset for each one. These high-confidence calls will serve as a baseline to evaluate the individual (*i.e.*, not merged) data generated by each participating laboratory to assess their performance. Benchmarking of SNVs and Indels will follow the guidelines developed

by GA4GH. Briefly, the set of variants to be benchmarked will be normalized with pre.py and then compared to the goldset with hap.py, restricting the analysis to the high confidence regions determined for each sample, obtaining the number of true positives (TP), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN), stratified by type of variant. These values will be used to compute the recall (a.k.a. sensitivity), the precision (a.k.a. specificity) and the F-score, a value that combines both metrics. The following formulas will be used to compute recall, precision and F-Score:

- $\text{Recall} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FN}) * 100$
- $\text{Precision} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FP}) * 100$
- $\text{F-Score} = 2\text{TP} / (2\text{TP} + \text{FP} + \text{FN})$

At a later stage, we will start the comparison of structural variants and generate their goldsets. The calls will be merged, and the variants will be stratified in tiers depending on the number of programs that identify them. Long reads from Oxford Nanopore Technology generated in a PromethION sequencer will be processed using the wf-human-variation pipeline, recommended by the vendor in the EPI2ME portal ([Link wf-human-variation](#)).

We will make reference datasets available to test new pipelines and assess them against the curated datasets.

Finally, reports will be written and guidelines will be made public.

9. References

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